

A Study On The Aquarium Fishes Of The Family Poeciliidae

Paper Id : 20420 Submission Date : 2025-07-04 Acceptance Date : 2025-07-20 Publication Date : 2025-07-23

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16450116

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Abstract

The present study aimed to provide the different morphological parameters of poeciliidae in aquarium conditions. The family poeciliidae of fishes is adaptable to aquarium life, and there are many colourful varieties available. They do not require much space or heat; generally they are not aggressive. The family includes about 30 genera and 293 species. It represents viviparous Cyprinodonts. These are the second group of ornamental fishes, after egg layers. It is a large family of small fishes, found naturally in many continents and countries like North and South America, U.S.S.R, Japan, Canada, Mexico, Argentina and India. The global distribution of Poeciliidae live-bearers is much wider than earlier it was (Faulkner and James, 1971).

Keywords

Poeciliidae, aquarium life, viviparous Cyprinodonts.

Introduction

Fishes enjoy a special consideration and place in the human civilization since time immemorial. Keeping tropical ornamental fishes is; wonderful hobby for many. The growing popularity of maintaining aquaria, is a part of pond of modern interior decoration. Poeciliidae are a family of freshwater ray-finned fishes of the order Cyprinodontiformes. Most members of this family are the tooth carps and include well-known live-bearing aquarium fish. The majority is hardy, of medium size, and they easily breed. Their lively behavior, colouring and tolerance of varying conditions make them ideal pet fishes. The genera of Poeciliidae that are commonly kept in aquaria are *Belonesox*, *Limia*, *Poecilia* and *Xiphophorus*.

Objective of study

The present study aimed to provide the different morphological parameters of poeciliidae in aquarium conditions.

Review of Literature

In these fishes mouth is slightly dorsal to anterior end of head. They have well developed small teeth in their jaws. Premaxillaries are slightly protractile; mandible prominent, teeth on jaws; palate edentate, gill membrane free from each other and also from isthmus. A large single dorsal fin without any spine can be seen. Lateral line is complete. The live-bearing toothed carps are also called topminnows, because of the tendency of many species of these basically small fishes to swim and feed near the water surface. Poeciliids are omnivores, i.e. they feed on a variety of plant and animal matter.

Methodology

A set of 30 healthy adult female and male Poeciliids individuals of the same age group in the equal ratio were put in a glass aquarium of 36x18x12 inches filled with potable water. The aquarium used was equipped with adequate illumination with essential requirements of plants and equipped with filter, a thermostat, an aerator pump and the accessories. Aquarium water was changed at regular intervals. A readymade Hitachi food along with some live food was given to them. Yellow and medicines were also added at some regular interval to control the bacterial and fungal growth in the aquarium water.

Result and Discussion

Our study noticed that these fishes are sexually dimorphic, which facilitates recognition for mating purpose. The male is expressed as polygamous and always the more active partner. Anterior margin of anal fin of is anterior to anterior margin of dorsal fin. The anal fin of females was noticed girthy, large and normal shaped. The presence of gonopodium, i.e., the modification of the anal fin in males into an intromittent organ and internal fertilization is a characteristic feature of live-bearing fishes (Chamber, (1987). This is used to insert the packets of sperms (spermozeugmata) into the female fish. It acts as the most significant external discriminatory feature between male and female and thereby, facilitating internal fertilization. It is widely regarded as the main external characteristic separating livebearers from all the other types of fish. In fact, the gonopodium is recognized as significant discriminatory feature and is supported internally by bony structures and moved backward, toward and side-ways.

A livebearer is a freshwater aquarium fishes that exotic facultative or obligate viviparity (Wourms, (1981). The young develops within the uterus of the mother and are nourished by the female's blood streams before birth. A pregnant female can be easily identified by a characteristic black spot or gravid spot, present at the posterior end of the gut near to the urinogenital vent. It is absent in case of males. It may be considered equivalent to the womb, but unlike mammals, the eggs contain an embryo well furnished with nutritive elements on which it feeds during development (Rosen and Tucker, 1961). The eyes of the developing fry were visible through the thin walls of the gravid spot. They give birth to fully develop young fishes.

Conclusion

The parental care is shown by viviparous teleosts (Baylis, 1981). Technically, they are not viviparous but ovoviviparous, producing normal spawn, but retaining it in the female's body until after hatching. The embryo undergoes development inside the eggs, sacs a process known as follicular gestation.

An interesting feature noticed in females is that a fertile female may have as many as half a dozen broods, even if no male were present in the breeding tank. This behavior may be attributed as a precautionary measure, and to store the packets of sperms ejected by the male and use them to fertilize a series of eggs and hatchlings as they ripen. Following a single mating, females produce a number of fry at regular intervals. This phenomenon is called superfecundation. They are prolific breeders and the young grows rapidly.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to the principal and managing secretary of Feroze Gandhi College, Raebareilly for providing the essential research facilities during this investigation.

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